

Direct long-read RNA sequencing uncovers functional variation affecting transcript production and RNA modifications.

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Keywords

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Abstract

The production of multiple transcripts per gene is a process regulated by inherited genetic variants and epitranscriptomic modifications, and plays a prominent role in modulating complex traits and diseases. To simultaneously characterize the effect of genetic variants on transcript abundance and N6-methyladenosine (m⁶A) modifications, we produced long-read native poly(A) RNA-seq data for 60 genetically different lymphoblastoid cell lines (LCLs) from the 1000 Genomes/Geuvadis project. We identified a high diversity of both annotated (40.2%) and unannotated (59.8%) transcripts, with only a small proportion expressed across individuals (35% and 18.4%, respectively). In a genome-wide genetic analysis on transcripts, we identified 87 trQTLs (transcript quantitative trait loci), of which 55 were not detected as eQTLs using a larger published short-read RNAseq dataset (317 samples). A population wide characterization of m⁶A methylation DRACH motifs (canonical m⁶A consensus sequence) identified an average of 4.04 m⁶A modifications on 4,325 genes. Genetic association analysis of highly variable modifications from 1,272 genes identified m⁶A modification quantitative trait loci (m⁶A-QTLs) for 5 transcripts. Even with a limited number of genetic associations, colocalization analysis of trQTLs and m⁶A-QTLs identified 8 candidate transcripts mediating GWAS traits, with approximately 75% of the colocalized trQTLs implicating novel risk transcripts, and an enrichment of GWAS lead variants involved in trQTLs. Overall, the simultaneous characterization of transcripts and post-transcriptional modifications identified genetic effects on transcription often missed when using other sequencing technologies.

Introduction

Alternative splicing (AS) is a molecular mechanism that produces a diversity of mRNA molecules from a single gene¹. By selecting different combinations of exons, genes produce multiple transcripts, which in turn can increase protein diversity²⁻⁴. Disruption of the splicing process has been associated with a large number of human diseases⁵⁻⁷, while the regulation of splicing by naturally occurring genetic variants is reported to play a prominent role in modulating complex traits and diseases^{1,8-11}. However, our knowledge about how an individual's genetic background may affect the production of specific transcripts after splicing is limited due to the lack of full transcript measurements in population-based studies. A population level transcript data would provide a catalog of individual transcripts, but the most used sequencing technology for assaying mRNA fractions transcripts before generating short-read sequences, requiring a computational reconstruction of transcripts which is prone to errors¹²⁻¹⁴. The process also requires an mRNA to cDNA conversion before sequencing, which removes most of the marks of post-transcriptional RNA modifications. These modifications influence the stability, dynamics, translation, and cellular location of RNA molecules, with implications for disease development¹⁵. Long-read sequencing can overcome these limitations by allowing the sequencing of transcripts in their native form, reconstructing their precise structures^{14,16}, identifying novel transcripts^{17,18}, and studying the allele-specific effects on transcript abundance and structure^{19,20} as well as identifying putative transcripts mediating genetic variant effects on disease risk.

Here, we investigated the influence of human genetic variation on gene expression using direct long-read RNA sequencing (DRS) of transcripts in their native form, from a population of 60 lymphoblastoid cell lines (LCLs) from the 1000 Genomes project²¹. Whole genome sequence was available from the New York Genome Center website and short-read RNA sequencing data were available from the Genetic European Variation in Disease project (Geuvadis)²¹⁻²³. With this data, we investigated *(i)* the distribution of annotated and novel transcripts across the population; *(ii)* the effect of genetic variants on directly measured transcript abundance, while *(iii)* characterizing some of the mechanisms by which SNPs affect gene and transcript expression. Moreover, *(iv)* we investigated the influence of human genetic variation on N6-methyladenosine (m⁶A) modifications in RNA molecules. This modification, present mostly in DRACH motifs (D-A, G, or U, R-A or G while H is A, C or U), is the most common RNA

modification in humans, with reports of up to one-quarter of transcripts in the human heart exhibiting this type of modification²⁴. Our findings have the potential to identify novel candidate transcripts mediating GWAS trait regulation that would be missed using traditional sequencing methods. Moreover, we could also study underlying processes influencing human complex traits, such as m⁶A modifications that often impact splicing, RNA structure, and translation.

Dataset overview

Total RNA from LCLs from 60 unrelated individuals of European ancestry²¹ were sequenced using a direct RNA sequencing (DRS) protocol to generate gene level and transcripts level quantification (**Supplementary Figure 1A-E**). We quantified total gene expression for 10,819 protein-coding genes and lncRNA genes that were expressed in at least 50% of the samples. This was a smaller number than the 14,712 genes detected using expression data from previously published short-read cDNA derived RNA-seq data (short-reads) from the same 60 LCL samples (**Figure 1A**)^{21,23}. This was likely driven by the lower sequencing yield produced by long-read sequencing (**Supplementary Figure 1F**), as shown by previous studies comparing short and long-read transcriptomics data for both short-reads and DRS^{19,25}. Most of the 4,273 additional genes discovered with short-reads were found to have low expression (**Figure 1A-B**). However, we were able to quantify the expression of 380 genes exclusively with DRS. These genes were significantly shorter than those detected across both technologies (pvalue = $6.8e^{-122}$, **Figure 1C**), in line with previous reports of bias towards better detection of longer genes by short-read sequencing²⁶. Finally, despite the described differences, we observed a consistent correlation of expression across samples for the 10,439 genes in common (median Spearman correlation 0.55 - 0.70, **Figure 1D**), in line with previous reports¹⁹.

Figure 1. Continuation. (C) Violin plots comparing gene length (bp) between all genes detected using DRS (dark yellow) and those only detected with DRS (yellow) (Wilcoxon pvalue= 3.4e-45); and between all genes detected with short-reads (dark red) and those only detected with short-reads and not with DRS (light red) (Wilcoxon pvalue=1.1e-149). (D) Pair-wise Spearman correlation between the overall gene expression in the same 60 LCLs samples among and between technologies. Bottom left histogram for DRS (median = 0.911) correlation across samples; top left histogram for short-reads (median = 0.950) ρ correlation across samples; and top right histogram for correlation between the two technologies is shown in the (median = 0.623). Ranges are shown on the x-axis. ρ (E) Heatmap with the number of annotated and novel transcripts per gene quantified by FLAIR after filtering for protein-coding and lincRNA genes expressed in at least 50% of the samples.

DRS identifies novel transcripts across individuals

Long-read RNA-seq data from multiple donors can identify the expression of individual-specific transcripts and thousands of novel transcripts by quantification of full transcripts with minimal computational reconstruction. Using FLAIR²⁷, we quantified the expression of 40,584 transcripts from 11,271 protein-coding genes and lincRNAs with a high mapping quality (>10) (**Table 1**). Of these, 59.8% were novel, defined as transcripts not included in the GENCODE v46 (hg38) reference annotation, and independently supported by SQANTI3 transcript classification, which integrates structural transcript features alongside existing annotations²⁸. On average, we detected 4.2 transcripts per gene across individuals, with 12.2% of genes expressing more than 5 novel transcripts (**Figure 1E**). Annotated transcripts had a significantly higher expression than non-annotated transcripts (Wilcoxon pvalue < 1e⁻²⁹⁶, **Supplementary Figure 2A**), with higher expressed genes showing a larger number of transcripts, both annotated and novel (**Supplementary Figures 2B-D**). This suggests that transcript annotations are biased towards highly expressed transcripts. Moreover, we observed that only 24.4% of all expressed transcripts (>5 TPMs) were observed in all individuals, with fewer novel transcripts (18.4%) expressed across all 60 individuals compared to annotated transcripts (35%). We also found 2,451 genes (20%) expressing only novel transcripts (**Supplementary Figure 3A-B**). Of these, 2,103 (86%) reported detectable expression in the previously published short-read gene-level summary quantification of the same LCL samples²³. Our findings suggest that many novel transcripts lacked annotations due to detection limitations and donor diversity, suggesting improvements on annotations may reduce the number of novel transcripts (see Supplemental Note). Moreover, they highlight the importance of generating and investigating transcripts diversity in a population setting.

A known property of multi-exon genes expressing multiple transcripts is that often one transcript dominates their expression in a specific cell or tissue^{29,30}. By defining genes with dominant transcripts as those with more than 90% of all the reads associated with one transcript, we found that 37% (4,543) of all expressed genes had a dominant transcript, of which 1,137 genes expressed only one transcript. We observed that genes with a dominant transcript had a higher mean expression than genes without dominant transcripts (Wilcoxon pvalue = $9.85e-228$, **Supplementary Figure 3C**). This was in agreement with previous reports showing that highly expressed protein-coding genes tend to code for one main protein isoform²⁹. We also observed that the majority of dominant transcripts were annotated (67.5%), suggesting that a high proportion of transcripts lacking annotation were not detected before due to low expression compared to known transcripts.

eQTLs and trQTLs discovery using DRS data

To detect genetic associations with gene expression, we performed a genome-wide expression quantitative trait loci (eQTL) analysis (see Methods) and discovered 26 significant eQTLs (FDR = 5%, **Figure 2A and Supplementary Table 1**). This is a considerably lower number than the 428 eQTLs discovered using the exact same 60 LCL samples and short-read data²³. The SNPs associated with DRS eQTLs (eSNPs) were located in close proximity to the transcription start site (TSS) of genes (**Figure 2A**), as expected from other eQTL studies^{31,32}. Genes with mapped eQTLs (eGenes) had a higher median expression than genes without an eQTL (**Figure 2B, Supplementary Figure 3D-F**), suggesting the lower sequencing yield of the newer technology limited discovery. DRS eGenes were also significantly shorter compared to the other genes (Wilcoxon pvalue = $4.197e^{-05}$), supporting our findings that long-read technologies provide some improvement to detect expression from shorter genes (**Figure 2C**). All in all, the lower sequencing yield obtained presents a strong limitation for population studies, however, newer technological developments are expected to overcome this.

Next, we performed a genome-wide cis transcript quantitative trait loci (trQTLs) analysis to identify genetic regulation of transcripts that were expressed in at least 50% of the samples (n = 40,584 from 11,271 genes). The analysis included annotated and novel transcripts and all SNPs in a 1Mb cis-window around each gene. To control for the lack of independence on the expression of transcripts from the same gene, we first performed a gene-level multiple testing correction across all transcripts and SNPs tested followed by a genome-wide correction (see

Methods). Reporting the most significant transcript-SNP pair per gene, we found more associations than for the gene quantification analysis, despite the higher multiple testing burden, with 87 significant trQTLs (FDR = 5%) also in close proximity to the TSS of the genes (**Figure 2D, Supplementary Table 2**). Only 14 genes had both eQTLs and trQTLs, with 8 involving the same SNP ($n=5$) or SNPs in high LD ($R^2>0.86$), none of the overlapping genes had dominant transcripts (**Supplementary Table 3 and Supplementary Figure 4A**). Transcripts with trQTLs had a significantly higher expression than transcripts without trQTL (Wilcoxon $pvalue = 4.61e^{-04}$, **Figure 2E**), and their genes had on average a higher number of transcripts than genes without significant transcript associations (8.86 and 3.56, respectively; **Figure 2F**). Genes with dominant transcripts were involved in only 3 of the trSNPs, and had a lower number of transcripts (**Figure 2G-H**). These results indicate that transcripts quantifications provide a more informative phenotype to characterize genetic effects on gene expression and can identify genetic associations not observable by standard eQTL analyses.

Figure 2. eQTL and trQTLs discovery using DRS data. (A) Scatter plot with all the SNPs tested for geneSNP associations. X-axis shows the SNP distance to the TSS of the gene (kbp); y-axis shows the $-\log_{10}$ pvalue for the association test. Red points identify significant eQTLs (26; FDR5%). (B) Violin plot comparing mean gene expression (TPM) between the 26 genes with a significant eQTL (red) and all the genes tested (blue) (Wilcoxon pvalue = $3.2e-07$). (C) Violin plot with gene lengths for genes with a significant eQTL signal (red) and all tested genes (blue) (Wilcoxon pvalue = $4.2e-05$). (D) Scatter plot with all the SNPs tested for transcript-SNP associations. X-axis shows the SNP distance to the TSS of the gene producing the transcript (kbp); y-axis shows the $-\log_{10}$ pvalue for the association test. Red points identify significant trQTLs (87; FDR5%). (E) Violin plot comparing mean transcript expression (TPM) between transcripts with a significant trQTL (eTranscripts, orange) and all tested transcripts (green) (Wilcoxon pvalue = $4.6e-04$). (F) Violin plots showing the different number of transcripts per gene on genes with a significant trQTL (eTranscripts, orange) compared to all the tested genes (green) (Wilcoxon pvalue = $4.95e-15$). (G) Violin plot comparing the $-\log_{10}$ pvalue of the 87 trQTL by whether the genes had a dominant transcript (orange) or not (yellow, Wilcoxon pvalue = $5.47e-03$). (H) Violin plot showing the difference in number of transcripts per gene on significant trQTL (eTranscripts) with dominant (orange) or non-dominant (yellow) transcripts (Wilcoxon pvalue = $1.58e-03$).

The identification of more trQTLs compared to gene-level eQTLs was driven by transcript specific effects which were missed when using gene-level summary phenotypes. We explored how often the same trSNP was associated with other transcripts from the same gene and how these compared to eQTLs from short and long reads quantifications derived from the sum of reads of all transcripts. A re-evaluation of the transcript significance within each gene (see Methods) found that more than half of our trSNPs (52 out of 87, 59.8%) were significantly associated with two ($n = 13$) or more ($n = 39$) transcripts per gene (**Supplementary Figure 4B**). For the majority of these 52 trSNPs (67.3%) the direction of the effect was opposite on at least one of the transcripts (**Supplementary Figure 4 C-D**), explaining the lower resolution to identify genetic associations using gene-level quantification. For example, we found that the trSNP rs35736654 was significantly associated with two out of six transcripts of the *CAST* gene (**Figure 3A**) with opposite directions of effect (**Figure 3B-C**). The effect of rs35736654 on *CAST* gene-level quantifications was not significant using long-reads gene expression (pvalue = 0.28, **Figure 3D**) but was nominally significant on the short-reads larger sample sized data (pvalue = $1.04e08$, **Figure 3E**). trQTLs were significant for two of the novel transcripts from *CAST*, a gene with no dominant transcript and a most abundant transcripts that accounted for only 30% of the total gene expression. In another example, the trSNP rs1177306 showed a significant association with three transcripts of *C2orf74*, with two transcripts showing effects in the same direction and one exhibiting an opposite direction of effect (**Figure 3F-I**). The gene level quantifications with short reads recapitulated the effects observed for the most significant of the trQTLs, also the overall most abundant transcript (ENST00000426997.5, pvalue = $5.4e-74$, **Figure 3J**), while they missed the association with other two novel less expressed transcript

(Figure 3I). This indicates that significant trQTLs often involve non-dominant transcripts, contributing to the difficulty in detection of genetic associations using gene quantifications.

Figure 3. Significant trQTL effects on the *CAST* and *C2orf74* genes. (A) Cartoon summarizing transcripts structure for the *CAST* gene. Transcripts marked with rectangular boxes and asterisks had significant trQTLs (blue and violet). Colors match figures B-E. (B-E) Violin-plots showing the mean expression of transcripts, as transcripts per million (TPM), grouped by genotype. Expression values correspond to covariate-adjusted residuals derived from normalized TPM (DRS) measurements. In (B) the violin plot of the effect of the SNP rs35736654 for a novel transcript (p-value = 1.05×10^{-11} , violet). In (C) the effect of the SNP rs357366548 for another novel transcript (p-value= 1.25×10^{-3} , blue). In (D and E), the violin plots show the effect of the SNP rs35736654 on *CAST* was not significant for gene quantifications from DRS (orange, p-value= 0.28) but significant for short-reads (red, pvalue = 1.04×10^{-8}) in concordance with effect shown in B). (F) Cartoon summarizing the structure of the transcripts detected with DRS for the *C2orf74* gene. Rectangular boxes and asterisk highlighting the transcripts affected by significant trQTLs (blue, green and violet). (G-I) Violin-plot showing the effect of the SNP rs1177306 on the known transcript ENST00000426997.5 (pvalue= 4.61×10^{-8} , blue), and two novel transcripts (pvalue= 2.1×10^{-3} , violet; pvalue= 3.6×10^{-3} , green). For the latter transcript (green) an sQTL was reported by GTEx (red junction in F). (J) Effect of the SNP rs1177306 on the *C2orf74* was also detected as an eQTL on gene expression detected by short-read sequencing (pvalue = 5.4×10^{-74}) with the same direction of effect as two of the transcripts.

These examples show how alleles can exhibit opposite effects on multiple transcripts from the same gene by affecting splice events detectable by splice-QTL (sQTL). These have been shown to change the number of sequence reads associated with a splice event, implying changes in the abundance of specific transcripts without necessarily altering the overall expression of the gene³³. Therefore, using sQTLs detected by the GTEx LCLs dataset ($n = 147^{32}$), we examined the extent to which transcript-level QTL associations reflect changes in splice events. After applying multiple-testing correction for all the transcript-SNP pairs from genes with sQTLs, we found that 31 trQTLs associations were supported by a significant sQTL (FDR = 0.05). Transcripts involved in both sQTL and trQTL were not significantly enriched for novel splice junction transcripts (NIC/NNC), which represent internal splice junction rearrangements detected by splice phenotypes (Fisher's exact test, OR = 0.37, $p = 0.05$), but were often reported as annotated splice forms (FSM/ISM, **Supplementary Figure 4G-H**). This suggests common sQTL-trQTL identified changes in the abundance of specific transcripts as a result of alternative splicing. For example, for the previously described *C2orf74* gene (**Figure 3**), GTEx reported a significant sQTL at the same locus, in high linkage disequilibrium (LD) with rs1177306 (rs11125869, $R^2=0.995$ in European population) affecting a junction, that is a sequence read spanning two exons, supporting a skipping event for the third exon of the gene (**Figure 3F**). Therefore, the effect of the sQTL implied a change in abundance of junctions characterizing the exon-including transcript and increased abundance of alternative transcripts, matching the effect observed at the transcript-level association for the novel light green transcript. Although this transcript was not the most significant trQTL signal at the locus, our

results support a splicing-mediated regulation modulating the abundance of transcripts of different structure. We therefore conclude that alternative splicing was the underlying biological process for many, but not necessarily all of the trQTLs.

Our results showed that the combination of QTL results from short and long-read technologies can contribute to characterizing biological processes underlying eQTLs, such as alternative splicing or effects on specific transcripts. However, given the sample size of the DRS dataset, low for genetic studies, we could only detect genetic signals affecting a small number of genes, even though most genes are expected to be affected by genetic variation^{31,32}. To overcome this limitation, and further explore the molecular processes underlying eQTL effects, we focused on the subset of previously reported significant eQTLs that were testable in our dataset. Specifically, of the 7,658 significant eQTLs identified from short-read RNA-seq in 317 LCL samples, 4,417 corresponded to genes with available quantifications in our dataset, and were therefore used for replication analyses²⁷. Contrary to our findings from the genome-wide analysis, we found a higher number of genes with significant eQTLs ($n = 213$, **Supplementary Table 4**) than trQTLs ($n = 186$ unique genes, **Supplementary Table 5**) using the long-reads dataset (FDR = 5%), with this approach also increasing the number of significant trQTLs to 303. Across analyses, these QTLs involved 327 unique genes, of which only 22% had significant associations for both, finding again only a limited overlap between eQTLs and trQTLs (**Supplementary Figure 4E**). Moreover, we found again that genes with a trQTLs had a higher number of transcripts compared to genes with an eQTL (Wilcoxon test p value = $8.84e^{-12}$, **Supplementary Figure 4F**). Since these comparisons were limited by the differences in the sample size of the short- and long-read studies (317 vs 60), we also estimated the proportion of associations from the alternative hypothesis (π_1), ranging from 0 to 1. Values closer to 1 indicate that a larger fraction of variants represent true associations, independent of statistical significance thresholds; this metric provides a power-adjusted estimate of replication that is less sensitive to differences in sample size between datasets.^{34,35}. Here, we estimated that of the short-reads eQTLs 25% ($\pi_1 = 0.25$) had evidence of being an eQTL ascertained with long read phenotypes, while for only 12% ($\pi_1 = 0.12$) was there evidence of acting as trQTLs. Moreover, a majority of trSNPs identified by the genome-wide analysis were not significantly associated in any of the gene-level eQTL analyses. As shown before, this could be driven by trSNPs of opposite direction of effect between transcripts of the same gene, but also pleiotropic

effects from SNPs in LD, and effects on lower expressed and nondominant transcripts, harder to detect using gene-level quantification.

Of the examples of trQTLs identified using a short-read eQTL information, we highlight here associations with the *OAS1* locus. We detected a mixture of annotated and novel transcripts (n=13) that share exon-intron architecture, with differences arising from exon length and terminal exon choices (**Figure 4A**). Several transcripts were reported as structurally different despite being highly similar, suggesting some novel transcripts may be the result of errors in transcription or on transcript modelling (**See Additional Note on Transcripts Identification, Figure 4A**). Consistent with this structural similarity, the SNP (rs1154970) of the most significant transcript per gene that is identified as the lead trQTL showed concordant transcript-level associations with comparable directions and magnitudes of effect on similar transcripts (**Figure 4B-C**, beta = -0.97 and -0.96 respectively). These similarities likely reflect challenges in transcripts modelling and read allocation while identifying the same genetic effects. In total, rs1154970 was nominally associated with ten of the thirteen observed transcripts (**Figure 4B-E, Supplementary Figure 7A, 6C**), with the two strongest associated transcripts showing decreased abundance with the alternative allele (**Figure 4B-C**) and additional transcripts showing increased abundance (**Figure 4D-E**). These opposite directions of effects resulted in no significant change in overall gene expression when assessed using DRS gene-level quantifications, and only nominal evidence of association in short-read gene-level analyses (**Supplementary Figures 5A-B**). We also observed a significant short-read eQTL for *OAS1* with a SNP (rs7132797) in high LD with rs1154970 ($R^2=0.96$), with an effect in the opposite direction of the lead transcript for the trQTL (**Supplementary Figure 5C and 5A**). This pattern is consistent with the presence of multiple regulatory variants acting on different layers of RNA processing, where an allele increasing gene expression can partially mask a transcript-specific regulatory effect when collapsing signal to the gene level. Together, these findings demonstrate how allelic heterogeneity and opposing transcript-specific effects can decouple transcript- and gene-level QTL signals, underscoring the importance of transcript-resolved analyses for uncovering genetically driven regulatory mechanisms.

More difficult to interpret were the genetic associations involving lowly expressed transcripts. An example involves the *ARPC2* gene, for which we report 22 distinct transcripts, of which a single annotated transcripts is the most abundant accounting for ~69% of all reads (**Figures**

4F, Supplementary Figure 6D). trQTL analysis identified rs2271541 as the strongest associated SNP with any transcript (**Figure 4G**). This lead association involved a lowly expressed novel transcript resulting from an intron retention event and predicted to undergo non-mediated decay (NMD) as a result of a premature termination codon (PTC) introduced by the retained intron and/or a frameshift (**Figure 4F**). This intron-retaining transcript is predicted to encode a truncated, NMD-prone protein (**Figure 4F bottom right**). The most abundant and annotated transcript was only nominally associated with rs2271541, with additional transcripts showing opposite directions of effects. Consistent with these differences in direction of effect, no eQTL was detected at the gene level, while short-read eQTL analysis identified a significant gene-level association for a SNP in high LD with the trQTL variant (**Supplementary Figures 5D-E**). These examples demonstrate the advantage of QTL analyses on transcript- rather than gene-level quantifications and exemplify the complicated processes involved in gene expression regulation.

Figure 4. Transcripts-specific effects of trQTL detected by long-reads. (A) Cartoon summarizing transcripts structure for the *OAS1* gene. Transcripts marked with rectangular boxes and asterisks had significant trQTLs (light and dark blue, violet and green). Colors match figures B-E. For the violet transcript (with an asterisk) GTEx also reported a significant sQTL (red junctions) and the dark blue transcript (ENST00000202917.10) also had a m6A modification on the final exon (red dots).

F**Transcripts of the *ARPC2* gene**

Figure 4. Continuation. (B-E) Violin-plots showing the mean transcript expression as transcripts per million (TPM) grouped by genotypes. Expression values correspond to covariate-adjusted residuals derived from normalised TPM (DRS); therefore values are centered around zero. (B) Shows the significant effect of the SNP rs1154970 on a novel transcript (pvalue= $4.23e^{-11}$, light blue). (C) We detected a similar effect on the known transcript ENST00000202917.10 with similar structure (pvalue= $5.97e^{-11}$, dark blue). (D-E) Violin-plot showing transcripts expression (TPM) grouped by genotypes for other 2 transcripts nominally significant for the association and with opposite direction of effect than the transcripts in B and C (pvalue= $3.94e^{-05}$ and $1.25e^{-03}$, green and violet respectively). (F) Cartoon summarizing the structure of the transcripts detected with DRS for the *ARPC2* gene. Rectangular boxes represent exons and connecting lines represent introns. Distinct colored tracks correspond to individual transcripts. The asterisk identifies a transcript significantly associated with rs2271541 resulting from an intron-retaining (IR) event, with dashed vertical lines marking the retained intronic segment across all transcripts. This IR event is predicted to introduce a premature termination codon (PTC), potentially triggering nonsense-mediated decay (NMD), in contrast to the canonical protein-coding transcript ENST00000315717.10_4. (G-H) Violin-plots showing transcript expression expressed (TPM) grouped by genotypes for the significant trQTL associations.

Genetic regulation of m⁶A RNA modifications abundance

N6-methyladenosine (m⁶A) modifications of RNA molecules are known to regulate pre-mRNA processing and mRNA stability. Previous studies have shown that human genetic variation regulates the abundance of RNA modifications by identifying m⁶A modifications

quantitative trait loci (m⁶A-QTLs) using m⁶A sequencing (m⁶A-seq). However, DRS technologies also allow the identification of m⁶A modifications without additional experiments. We identify RNA modifications on transcripts using m⁶Anet³⁶, which reports the ratio of reads with m⁶A modifications over unmodified bases per transcript on DRACH motifs (D–A, G, or U, R–A or G while H is A, C or U). After quality assessments, we identified 17,491 m⁶A RNA modification events on 15 motifs detected in at least one transcript and one individual (**Supplementary Figure 8A, C**). These modifications were detected on transcripts from 4,325 unique genes, with a mean of 4.04 modifications per gene. We observed that transcripts with m⁶A modification were coded by genes with a higher number of transcripts, both novel and annotated, compared to genes with low probability of having m⁶A (Wilcoxon pvalue = 4.43e⁻²⁴⁸ annotated, < 2.2e-16 novel and < 2.2e-16 all transcripts, **Supplementary Figure 8E-G**). Most modifications mapped to exonic regions (97.5%), including coding sequences in untranslated regions (UTRs) in 3' and 5' UTRs (**Figure 5A**). Although not directly comparable, these numbers were lower than those reported by m⁶A-seq experiments in human tissues, including LCLs^{37,38}, which may simply reflect again the lower sequencing yield or the lower resolution of the flow cells used here ³⁹.

To identify m⁶A-QTLs, we selected m⁶A modifications detected in at least 50% of the samples (**Supplementary Figure 8B**) limiting our analysis to 2,761 modifications from 1,272 unique genes (2.17 mean modifications per gene) (**Supplementary Figure 8D**). To allow comparison with other QTLs, we tested all SNPs in the same 1Mb window around the TSS of the genes, controlling for multiple testing across modifications per gene and reporting the best modification-SNP association per gene. After genome-wide multiple testing correction, we detected 5 significant m⁶A-QTLs (FDR 10%) (**Supplementary Table 6**). The significantly associated m⁶A-QTLs included SNPs in intronic (2; 40%), downstream (1; 20%), upstream (1; 20%), and intergenic (1; 20%) regions (**Supplementary Table 7**). Next, we investigated if SNP were often located in the modified motifs. Among all the RNA modifications detected (n = 17,491) only 1.16% had a SNP as part of their motif (203) and only 1.2% of the motifs tested for m⁶A-QTLs (34 out of 2,761) (**Supplementary Table 8**). None of the 5 motifs involved in m⁶A-QTLs contain a SNP in the sequence. Our results indicate that DRS is suitable for identifying genetic effects modulating the proportion of transcripts with m⁶A modifications.

To evaluate the DRS-detected m⁶A modifications with an orthogonal method, we compared our modification sites with m⁶A peaks identified in Yoruba LCLs from the 1000 Genomes Project with m⁶A sequencing (m⁶A-seq), an antibody-based enrichment method³⁸. After exon-aware transcript-to-genome mapping (See Methods), 58% of all DRS-detected m⁶A modifications overlapped with m⁶A-seq peaks assigned to the same gene (61% when relaxing the requirement for gene concordance). This concordance was substantially higher for modifications detected across multiple samples: among the 2,761 m⁶A modifications tested for m⁶A-QTL mapping and detected in 50% of the samples, 72.6% overlapped a m⁶A-seq peak within the same gene. Only one of the significant m⁶A-QTLs overlapped a corresponding m⁶A-seq peak and a m⁶A-QTL in the Yoruba dataset, involving the *CALR* gene, with a significant m⁶A-QTL with the same lead SNP (rs2974751) and the same direction of effect in both datasets (**Figure 5B**).

To better understand the processes mediating m⁶A-QTLs, we investigated how often significant eQTL and sQTLs acted as m⁶A-QTLs. We re-evaluated the 7,657 eQTLs identified in the larger short-reads data (317 samples)²³, of which 550 affected genes with a motif tested in our m⁶A-QTL analysis. We tested whether the eQTL variant was also associated with the m⁶A ratio phenotype and after multiple testing correction, two were significant (FDR < 5%). We estimated that for 19% of the tested genes, the eQTL also affected m⁶A ratio ($\pi_1=0.193$). Moreover, of the 733 genes with sQTLs in GTEx LCLs evaluated for m⁶A-QTL, only two sQTLs were also associated with m⁶A ratio, *OAS1* and *DAP* ($\pi_1=0$)³². Expression phenotypes from the *OAS1* gene were also associated with three variants in strong LD with effects on transcripts (rs1154970), gene expression (rs7132797), and splicing in GTEx (rs10774671; **Figure 4A**). All three variants had nominally significant associations with m⁶A ratios involving the same DRACH motif (GGACT), with consistent direction of effect (**Figure 5C**). A conditional m⁶A-QTL analyses revealed that the association for each variant was strongly attenuated after conditioning on the other SNPs, and reverse conditional analyses showed that neither the lead eQTL nor the splice variant retained a significant association with m⁶A after conditioning on the lead trQTL rs1154970 (**Supplementary Figure 9A**). Together, the convergence across molecular phenotypes generated from different data types and experiments (GTEx, Geuvadis, and our study)^{22,23,32} suggests all molecular phenotypes are capturing the genetic regulation of a similar biological process which remains unclear, as splicing and m⁶A modifications are known to be coupled processes. The lead SNP (rs10774671) is known as a

functional splice-altering variant that generates distinct *OAS1* protein isoforms (p42 versus p46), with the A allele here associated with reduced *OAS1* expression, and reported for impaired antiviral activity, and increased severity of COVID-19⁴⁰. Our results suggest a model in which the genetic effect observed may reflect a change in the abundance of m⁶A reads regulating splicing and therefore influence transcripts abundance, or a change in transcript abundance and structure with the number of m⁶A modified reads being fixed by an independent process. Consistent with this interpretation, *OAS1* has previously been shown to be regulated by m⁶A methylation and to play a key role in interferon-mediated antiviral responses⁴¹. Overall, using DRS we identified genetic effects influencing the relative abundance of m⁶A modification on transcripts potentially coupled with splicing and transcript structure regulation, without the need of additional experiments, contributing to our understanding of the underlying processes regulating gene expression.

Figure 5. m⁶aRNA modifications and m⁶aQTL effects. (A) Motif analysis of the RNA modifications identified on the m⁶A DRACH consensus motif (D–A, G, or U, R–A or G while H is A, C or U) (upper panel) and guitar plot showing the distribution of m⁶A modifications along the gene bodies (lower panel). (next page)

Figure 5. Continuation. (B-C) Violin-plot showing the genotype versus m⁶A RNA modification ratio (modified reads/total reads, normalised and with covariates regressed out), where outliers are shown as black dots; in (B) the significant effect of the SNP rs2974751 on the ratio of reads with the RNA modification on the GGACT motifs of the CALR transcript (ENST00000316448 pvalue=3.7e-15, purple). (C) The significant effect of the SNP rs1154970 on the ratio of read RNA modifications on the GGACT motifs for the OAS1 transcript (ENST00000202917.1, pvalue=6.8e-03, purple). (D) LocusCompare plots showing a ~1 Mb region centered on the lead trQTL SNP (rs6940814) for the gene PEX6, which colocalizes with a GWAS signal for non-HDL cholesterol. The top panel shows GWAS association summary statistics and the lower panel shows trQTL association statistics. The x-axis represents genomic position on chromosome 6 (Mb), and the y-axis shows $-\log_{10}(P)$ values for the associations, for GWAS or trQTL. Each point corresponds to a SNP, colored according to linkage disequilibrium (r^2) with the lead SNP (rs6940814). (E) LocusCompare plots for the m⁶A-QTL (rs4808779) in the gene JUND, which colocalizes with a GWAS signal for non-HDL cholesterol.

GWAS colocalization

Genetic effects on gene expression are often used to identify genes mediating the activity of genetic variants on complex traits identified using GWAS. To evaluate the possible benefits of identifying genes mediating GWAS loci activity using quantifications from transcripts and m⁶A modifications, we first look at the overlap of significant SNPs with the GWAS catalog⁴²⁻⁴⁴ and then performed a colocalization analysis with 10 traits (**Supplementary Table 11**). Of the 87 trSNPs identified, 18 (20.7%) were reported as lead variants for 14 broad GWAS trait categories (91 catalog entries), including lipids/cholesterol, blood cell traits, plasma protein levels, kidney function, and immune/autoimmune diseases. Testing a random set of SNPs with similar properties (Methods), found that trSNPs were enriched in GWAS lead variants (OR = 4.25, fisher test pvalue = 3.74e-05). In addition, 12 trQTL signals showed strong colocalization with 5 GWAS associations (COLOC probability PP.H4 > 0.9, **Supplementary Tables 9-11**), supporting a shared genetic basis. Approximately 75% of these trQTLs were associated with novel transcripts, highlighting the contribution of transcript-specific regulation. Among the 5 SNPs involved in m⁶A-QTLs, 2 (40%) were previously identified as lead GWAS variants across 4 broad trait categories (10 catalog entries) including blood cell traits and plasma protein levels. As an example, we identified a trQTL (rs6940814) at the PEX6 locus colocalizing with a non-HDL cholesterol GWAS signal (**Figure 5D**). *PEX6* encodes an ATPase involved in peroxisome biogenesis and lipid metabolism⁴⁵, suggesting that transcript-specific regulation at this locus may influence lipid-related traits through modulation of peroxisomal function. Similarly, at the *TMBIM1* locus, a trQTL colocalizes with an inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) GWAS signal (**Supplementary Figure 9B**). *TMBIM1* has been implicated in the

regulation of apoptosis and inflammatory signaling pathways, supporting a potential role for transcript-specific regulation in immune-related disease mechanisms⁴⁶. We also identified a m⁶A-QTL at the *JUND* locus that colocalizes with a non-HDL cholesterol GWAS signal (COLOC PP.H4 = 0.93; **Figure 5E**). *JUND* encodes a component of the AP-1 transcription factor complex, which regulates cellular stress responses and metabolic pathways, suggesting that variation in RNA modification may contribute to trait-associated regulatory programs⁴⁷. Our results show that even with modest sample sizes leveraging underexplored molecular phenotypes, such as transcripts and RNA modifications, can uncover candidate genes and mechanisms underlying GWAS signals. They also highlight how incomplete transcript annotation underestimates true transcriptomic complexity, limiting the ability of current QTL studies to interpret GWAS signals.

Discussion

In this study, we performed sequencing of mRNA molecules in their native form using long-read direct RNA sequencing (DRS) from 60 of the 1000 Genomes project samples. We report similar read length distributions and quality to previous studies using long read sequencing of cDNA reads from mRNA (cDNAseq)²⁵, and high correlation with expression from short reads in the same LCL samples²³. DRS however, did provide lower sequencing coverage, limiting discovery of genetic associations compared to short-read RNA-seq. Lower coverage has been reported before for this technology^{25,48}, but newer developments are already providing better quality data and higher resolution for population studies⁴⁹. All in all, and just as eQTL studies using exon quantifications typically find more eQTLs than gene-level studies^{34,50}, transcript quantifications and transcript centric analyses⁵¹ were able to identify genetic effects missed using the aggregate gene-level expression. Ultimately, we were able to report that 7% of significant eQTLs identified with short-reads and a larger sample size were the results of changes in the expression of specific transcripts (trQTLs), helping to untangle the nature of the genetic regulation.

Long-read sequencing identifies novel candidate genes that mediate the activity of GWAS variants missed by other methods. These new findings are mostly provided by the better biological resolution and additional information provided by the data generated. Transcripts provide a more direct characterization of gene products, resulting in a larger number of genetic

associations, just as has been reported before for exon and other transcript aware methods and technology^{34,51}. As a consequence, we were able to detect trQTLs colocalizing with GWAS loci. We noted that the majority of those signals were associated with novel transcripts, highlighting not only the improvement in identifying genes mediating GWAS variants activity but also the importance of better molecular phenotype annotations. These findings suggest that previously unannotated transcripts may represent functional intermediates linking genetic variation to disease risk. However, it is not clear how many of the thousands of novel transcripts reported using long-read sequencing methods^{19,42,49} may be the result of sequencing or computational artifacts derived from the tools used to reconstruct transcripts. Our main analyses were done on transcript quantifications generated using FLAIR. An extensive benchmarking work done by Pardo-Palacios et al⁵² recommended FLAIR for identifying sample-specific transcriptomes in well-annotated organisms, and for reliable quantification, supporting our choice for this study. Our own comparative analyses (**Supplementary Note**) using Bambu⁵³ and StringTie2⁵⁴ in addition to FLAIR, agreed with previous studies in that different tools find different transcripts, with each tool presenting their own biases. The trQTLs detected by each method showed that genetic associations involving annotated transcripts were well replicated with the larger differences observed for trQTLs involving novel transcripts. This may be driven by differences in quantifications, with conservative methods assigning more reads to a smaller number of reference-compatible transcripts and fewer reads distributed across multiple transcripts, but also to the higher resolution to quantify annotated transcripts as those tend to be more expressed. Ultimately, researchers should carefully consider what tool better suits their needs based on their research question and considering biases. For example, Bambu did not identify annotated transcripts with alternative 5' or 3' endings. For genetic associations, we recommend considering how important it is for the aims of the study to report individual variability or uncover associations missed by other methods over the reliability of finding genetic associations for further, potentially costly, experimental studies. If the latter is the main aim, then annotation reliant methods are recommended. Here, we aimed to evaluate the added value of using DRS to identify novel genetic associations often missed by other methods. For this objective, we believe FLAIR provided a reasonable balance between novel and annotation reliant modeling.

Our analysis reported trQTLs more often for genes without a dominant transcript. It has been suggested that cells tend to express transcripts that preserve the conserved structural and

functional features of the proteins they code²⁹. This would imply that dominant transcripts, potentially more conserved, would be less tolerant of variation, harboring fewer trQTLs. However, multiple studies have found that transcriptome diversity decreases for highly expressed genes⁵⁵ in contradiction with other studies indicating the opposite effect was true⁵⁶. Moreover, Pickrell et al,⁵⁷ found that introns in highly expressed genes are spliced more accurately, likely due to their shorter length, suggesting that a combination of characteristics needs to be considered. The overall implication is that protein production may be regulated by altering the balance between functional and non-functional transcripts⁵⁸, suggesting that dominant transcript expression could be a mechanism to ensure particular protein isoforms are produced in sufficient quantities. This suggests that the expression of a dominant transcript is a transient property of the gene under genetic and environmental regulation. In the context of our results, it is important to consider that only ~37% of expressed genes meet our stringent dominance definition (>90% of reads mapping to a single transcript), with the majority of genes lacking a unique dominant transcript. Any postulation should also take into account the limited number of trQTLs identified. However, we favor an explanation rooted in transcript architecture and transcript complexity: genes with multiple co-expressed transcripts provide greater opportunity for cis-regulatory variants to modulate transcript proportions without substantially altering total gene expression. Such effects would be detectable at the transcript level but may not manifest as conventional gene-level eQTLs.

An additional advantage of DRS is the ability to directly evaluate the influence of post-transcriptional chemical modifications of RNA molecules without the need for additional experiments. We detected a lower number of modifications than previously reported in different tissues⁵⁹, but many of the signals overlapped those reported by other sequencing methods^{37,38}. Their distribution along the genes was also in agreement, with the vast majority falling in introns, exons, and 3'UTR regions of genes, highlighting their relevance for transcription regulation and structure. We estimated that approximately 19% of genes with eQTLs likely harbor m⁶A-QTL effects, while our estimates for sQTLs was 0%, suggesting broader gene expression phenotypes may capture some of the modification effects but not the precise splicing-related effects. This seemingly contradicts the expectation that m⁶A should relate to splicing phenotypes, given that splicing and m⁶A modification are known to be coupled processes⁶⁰. However, the smaller number of m⁶A-QTL here identified limits our interpretation of these results and calls for further work. In any case, we were able to provide

one example of shared genetic regulation of multiple expression phenotypes for the OAS1 locus, using different data types and experiments (splicing from GTEx, short and long read sequencing)^{23,32}. Our analyses suggest that all molecular phenotypes were capturing the genetic regulation of a similar biological process but the biological mechanism for the m⁶A-QTL remains unclear. We may be detecting a change in the abundance of m⁶A modifications regulating splicing and therefore influencing transcripts abundance, or a change in transcript abundance and structure with the number of m⁶A modified reads being fixed by an independent process. Future work with larger and better datasets may be able to disentangle this relationship and clarify the precise mechanism underlying the genetic regulation of m⁶A modifications which could provide insights into new mechanisms by which genetic variants can influence disease risk.

Material and Methods

LCL samples

The 60 LCLs were from the 1000 Genomes Project cohort with European ancestry and from unrelated individuals²¹. All the samples are part of the NHGRI sample repository for human genetic research. All LCLs came from the Coriell Institute for Medical Research (Camden, New Jersey, USA). LCLs were grown under identical conditions in RPMI 1640 media supplemented with 1% penicillin-streptomycin, 1% L-glutamine, and 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS). LCLs were cultured for at least 3 to 4 weeks until their exponential growth phase and had a total concentration of at least 4×10^7 LCLs and a constant high viability (~98%). All cells were tested for mycoplasma contamination (Lonza, MycoAlert mycoplasma detection kit) before being used for the following steps.

RNA extraction, library preparation, and sequencing

From 4×10^7 mycoplasma-free LCLs we obtained total RNA using Trizol Reagent (Invitrogen). Cells were washed twice with 1×phosphate-buffered saline (Invitrogen) to remove all the media and 1ml of Trizol was added per $5-10 \times 10^6$ cells in each sample, incubated for 5min at room temperature (RT), and transferred to Eppendorf tubes. The rest of the protocol followed the manufacturer's guidelines with the addition of 200µl of chloroform for every ml of Trizol for the phase separation followed by mixing and centrifuging for 15min at $2000 \times g$ at 4°C. The

phase containing RNA was recovered and transferred in new Eppendorf tubes for RNA precipitation with 500µl of isopropanol for every 1ml of Trizol and incubation at RT for 15min followed by centrifugation 20min at 2000×g at 4°C. After RNA precipitation, 70% ethanol was used to wash the pellet and centrifuged 5min at 2000×g at 4°C, the supernatant was discarded, and the RNA pellet was air dried for 5-10min. The pellet was solubilized in 20µl of 0.5% SDS in RNase-free water. No DNase treatment was applied.

The total RNA was quantified using Qubit Fluorometer 2.0 with the Qubit RNA Broad Range (BR) Assay kit according to the manufacturer's instructions (Thermo Fisher) and Nanodrop to exclude the presence of alcohol and protein contaminants that could interfere with the sequencing, keeping RNA samples with a ratio OD_{260/280} of at least 1.9 and ratio OD_{260/230} > 1.5. Agilent Bioanalyzer RNA 6000 Nano Kit (Agilent) was used to assess the quality and integrity of RNA. Only samples with RNA Integrity Number (RIN) >8.9 were used for the following steps. The total RNA was then poly-A⁺ tailed before the library preparation using the Dynabeads™ mRNA Purification Kit (Thermo Fisher). The poly-A⁺ tailed capture step was repeated re-using the same Dynabeads, which increased the enrichment of poly-A⁺ tailed RNA and improved the consequent elimination for ribosomal RNA. The final quantification of poly-A⁺ tailed RNA was performed by the TapeStation with High Sensitivity RNA ScreenTape (Agilent) to ensure the quasi-total elimination of the 28S and 16S ribosomal peaks.

For the library preparation, we used 500ng poly-A⁺ tailed RNA in a total volume of 9µl and followed all the steps of the ONT protocol for the Direct RNA Sequencing Kit (updated version 27/12/2019 nanoporetech.com, cat# SQK-RNA002). The quantification of the library RNA was performed using the Qubit fluorometer DNA HS assay (Thermo Fisher) - recovery aim of ~200ng. Then, before loading the RNA into the FLOW-MIN106D flow cell, the numbers of pores and properly primed pores were checked according to the manufacturer's instructions. Finally, the sequencing was carried on for 72h on the GridION Mk1 sequencing device (ONT) that allows sequencing of a maximum of five samples in each run, one per flow cell.

Pre-processing of RNA sequencing data

Base-calling was performed using the Guppy software (from ONT, v 3.2.10) in the *high accuracy mode*. Guppy used the *fast5* files generated by the ONT Device Control software (MinKNOW), embedded in the GridION sequencing device, as input to (i) generate a *fastq* file

for each *fast5* file containing the base-called sequences; (ii) create base-called *fast5* files. (iii) classify *fastq* and *fast5* files into pass/fail folders according to the average quality score of each read (above 7.0), and (iv) make summary files for every flow cell sequenced. We applied the specific options suggested in the Direct RNA sequencing protocol taking into consideration the reversed direction of the sequencing (3'→5'), the presence of uracil instead of thymine, and an optimized strategy for trimming the adapter's raw signal. We used only the passing reads for the following analysis.

Mapping sequences. We concatenated the *fastq* files obtained from base-calling into a single *fastq* file. These *fastq* files were then mapped to the reference human genome GRCh37 (hg19_chr_only_and_herpes.fa) using minimap 2 v2.12⁶¹. The calling was performed in a splicing-aware manner with the following options: *minimap2 -a -x splice -k14 -uf* (-a -x splice: splice alignment mode; -uf: force minimap2 to consider the forward transcript strand only; -k14: small k-mer to increase sensitivity to the first or the last exons). Alignment files from minimap2 were converted to *bam* format, sorted, and indexed using samtools v1.23⁶².

Data quality control (QC). We applied Nanoplot (v1.33.0)⁶³ to produce QC graphs displaying multiple aspects of sequencing raw data; while NanoStat (v1.4.0) was used to obtain a statistical data summary⁶³. The pycoQC tool (v2.5.2)⁶⁴ served to generate an interactive QC report from the base caller's datasets. Specifically, pycoQC uses the sequencing summary file generated by Guppy and the *bam* / *sam* file to generate a pre / post-alignment QC report.

Gene quantification.

We used *featureCounts* to provide the gene-level counts (from Subread v1.6.0) to the genome alignments using exons as the feature type⁶⁵. We used the *-L* argument of *featureCounts* to enable the long-read mode with a minimum overlap of 10 bases (*--minOverlap 10*) and we used GENCODE v46 as the reference annotation⁶⁶. To ensure consistency with Illumina short-read gene quantification and enable direct comparisons across platforms, we used the GRCh37 reference genome built from a lift-over of GENCODE v46 to GRCh37. Raw counts were converted to RPKM (Reads Per Kilobase of transcript, per Million mapped reads) using the *rpkM* function of the edgeR package (v3.9)⁶⁷.

Transcript quantification and characterization

To identify transcripts from the native RNA sequences we used FLAIR v3.0.0 (<https://github.com/BrooksLabUCSC/flair>)²⁷. For the analysis, *bam* files obtained using the minimap2 aligner were converted to *bed* format using the bam2bed12.py script provided with FLAIR. FLAIR-*correct* was used to correct the splice-site boundaries of reads. It corrected misaligned splice sites using genome annotations from GENCODE v46 and GRCh37 as the reference genome. Next, the FLAIR-*collapse* command processed the corrected reads, generating a first-pass transcripts set. To do this, FLAIR-*collapse* grouped reads on their splice junction chains and only kept transcripts supported by at least 10 reads and mapping quality >10. At this step, the first-round alignments were split by chromosome due to computational limitations. FLAIR-*quantify* was used to determine transcript levels in all samples where reads aligned to annotated transcripts (GENCODE v46). The 42,065 transcripts not aligning with any gene in the GENCODE v46 annotation were excluded from the following analyses. Reads were normalized using transcripts per million (TPM) normalization. Moreover, mitochondrial transcripts as well as transcripts supported by less than 10 reads and expressed with less than five TPMs in at least one sample were excluded. To characterize and refine transcript structural annotations, we used SQANTI3²⁸, classifying transcripts based on their splice junction composition, transcript structure, and concordance with reference annotations. Transcripts with incongruent or ambiguous structural classifications following the initial FLAIR annotation were re-classified using the SQANTI3 reclassification framework, allowing more precise assignment of full-splice-match, incomplete-splice-match, and novel transcript categories. Additionally, 272 transcripts assigned conflicting classifications, appearing as both directly annotated and novel-annotated due to redundant matching across the two-step FLAIR annotation strategy, were removed from both groups to avoid double-counting. The SQANTI3-refined transcript classifications were used in all downstream analyses. Transcripts with intron chains not matching any transcripts in the reference annotation (GENCODE v46) and not classified as full splice matches (FSM) or incomplete splice matches (ISM) to annotated transcripts by SQANTI3 were defined as '*novel transcripts*'.

In addition to FLAIR-based transcript quantification, we performed transcript-level quantification using Bambu⁵³ and StringTie⁵⁴ to enable method comparison and assess the robustness of transcript abundance estimates. Both new methods performed transcript discovery and quantification using the same minimap2-aligned BAM files and the GENCODE

v46 annotation as the initial reference, and only protein coding genes and lncRNA genes were investigated. For Bambu, we used a multi-sample framework with transcript discovery enabled (discovery = TRUE) in stranded mode, and a novel discovery rate (NDR) threshold was estimated by Bambu and set to 0.1, corresponding to a recommended baseline false discovery rate. The resulting extended transcript annotation was then used for transcript-level quantification (quant = TRUE) across all samples. StringTie was run in long-read mode with reference guidance enabled (-L, -G), a minimum transcript coverage threshold of 1.5 reads (-c 1.5), a 50 bp gap for transcript merging (-g 50), and multithreading enabled (-p 8). Gene-level abundance estimates were generated using the -A option. Resulting transcript models and abundance estimates were used for comparison with FLAIR- and Bambu-based quantification (**Supplementary Note**). To further refine transcript structural annotations, transcripts with ambiguous or incongruent classifications were reclassified using SQANTI3²⁸, and the SQANTI3-refined classifications were used in downstream analyses.

RNA-seq data and genotype data from external datasets

Curated short-read Illumina RNA-seq data and genotype data of 60 LCLs were used as described in Delaneau et al.²³. Briefly, gene expression was quantified using QTLtools (v1.3.3)⁶⁸ with GENCODE v19⁶⁶ as the reference gene annotation. In the original study, genes were filtered to retain only protein-coding genes and long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) expressed in more than 90% of the samples. The gene expression was quantified using RPKM units for the gene expression quantification in the ONT dataset. The genotype data for these samples, available from either the 1000 Genomes project or the Illumina Human OMNI 2.5M SNP array, were filtered using standard procedures to remove low-quality SNPs. Specifically, variants were excluded based on low call rate (<95%), minor allele frequency (MAF <1%), and deviation from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium ($P < 1 \times 10^{-6}$)²³. Moreover, the resulting genotype matrix of 317 individuals and 9,255,024 variants was imputed from the 1000 Genomes phase 3 reference panel²¹, and variants with low imputation quality (INFO score <0.8) were removed²³.

Gene expression correlation between short-reads and DRS long-reads seq dataset

Pair-wise gene expression Spearman correlations were computed between Illumina short-reads and DRS long-reads from the same 60 LCLs samples using the *rcorr* function in the *corrplot*

R package (v0.92)⁶⁹. Both gene expression datasets included protein-coding genes and lncRNAs expressed in at least 50% of their samples, of which $n = 10,439$ were found in both sets.

Molecular quantitative trait loci

For each molecular phenotype, gene abundance, and transcript abundance, we identify QTLs using the QTLtools software package (v1.3.1)⁶⁸. Gene expression from short-read sequencing was quantified as RPKM, and transcript expression from long-read (DRS) sequencing was quantified as TPM. These normalized expression values were used as phenotypes in QTLtools. Covariates (sex, sequencing technology, genotype principal components, and expression PCs) were included directly in the QTLtools linear regression model during association testing. All genetic variants within ± 1 Mb of the transcription start site were associated with the phenotypes, and the best-associated SNP (i.e., with the smallest nominal pvalue) was retained. After that, the nominal pvalues were adjusted for the number of variants being tested using 1,000 permutations. This is implemented in the *cis* mode of the QTLtools software package (v1.3.3)⁶⁸. Multiple testing correction across phenotypes was done using the qvalue package in R (version 2.18.0)³⁵ to identify all significant phenotype-variant pairs at 5% False Discovery Rate (FDR). For eQTL analysis, we tested genes expressed in at least 50% of the samples ($n = 10,820$). For the trQTL analysis, we tested annotated and novel transcripts expressed in at least 50% of the samples ($n = 40,585$) which corresponded to 11,271 unique genes. For trQTL analysis, we used the option *-grp* to correct and account for multiple phenotypes (transcripts) per gene. This option performs a permutation pass at the gene group level across all phenotype-SNP pairs per gene to discover gene-level trQTLs. All QTL analyses included the following covariates: sex, sequencing technology, the first three principal components (PCs) from genotypes, and three and one PCs from expression genes and transcripts, respectively. The number of phenotype PCs included as covariates was determined empirically by testing several configurations and selecting the one that optimized QTL discovery while adequately controlling for confounding effects.

Short-reads eQTL recapitulation in DRS long-reads dataset

The eQTLs already identified using 317 samples from the Illumina RNA-seq data described in Delaneau et al.²³ were used. From these 7,658 significant eQTLs in the Illumina dataset, only

4,417 involved genes and transcripts expressed in at least 50% of the samples that were kept as part of the DRS long-reads dataset. To detect how many of the significant short-reads eQTL were also detected in long-read native RNA-seq, we extracted the p-values from the same phenotype-SNP pair associations and calculated π_1 using the *q-value* package in R³⁵. The *q-value* estimation for false discovery rate control R package (v2.18.0) used a $\lambda = 0.05$ and FDR = 0.05.

To detect how many of the 87 significant trQTLs we discovered have a significant effect on multiple transcripts produced by the same gene, we extracted the nominal p-values from the same phenotype-SNP pair associations and calculated π_1 using the *q-value* package in R (v2.18.0)³⁵. The *q-value* estimation for false discovery rate control R package (version 2.18.0) used a $\lambda = 0.05$ and FDR = 0.05.

RNA modifications

The m⁶A RNA modifications detection was performed using m⁶Anet tool³⁶ that was specifically trained on dataset sequenced using the DRS SQK-RNA002 kit. We follow the general pipeline starting from the alignment to the transcriptome reference using nanopolish tools (v0.14.0)⁷⁰, the data prep step, and the inference step. m⁶Anet performs a sampling process by selecting 20 reads from each candidate site. The probability of modification is averaged over 1000 rounds of sampling and the resulting data contains the probability of modification for each individual read. The software also outputs the estimated percentage of reads at a given site that is modified per sample. This is the phenotype used for further analyses. As recommended by the authors, we kept only modifications reported with a probability >0.9.

Filter on modifications: 17,941 modifications were found in at least one transcript and one individual on 4,321 protein coding genes or lncRNAs as reported by Gencode v46⁶⁶. Next, we remove any modifications with more than 50% missing values or probabilities <0.9. That left 2,761 modifications from 1,272 genes for evaluation. m⁶A sites detected by m⁶Anet were reported as positions relative to spliced transcript sequences. Transcript-relative positions were mapped to genomic coordinates using exon structures from the corresponding GENCODEv46 annotation by computing cumulative exon lengths in a strand-aware manner and identifying the exon containing each site.

m⁶A RNA modification molecular quantitative trait loci

For m⁶AQTL analysis, we tested RNA modifications expressed in at least 50% of the samples, leaving a total of 2,761 modifications from 1,272 genes for QTL analysis. The ratio of modified reads over the total of reads per transcripts were quantile normalize, as per gene and transcript expression. As for trQTLs, we employed the "-grp" option to correct for and consider multiple phenotypes (modifications) associated with each transcript. This option conducts a permutation process at the transcript group level across all phenotype-SNP pairs per transcript, enabling the identification of transcript-level m⁶A-QTLs. All QTL analyses included the following covariates: sex, the first three principal components (PCs) from genotypes, and three PCs from expression (RNA modifications). We used FDR to correct for multiple testing, reporting significant associations with FDR<10%.

Short-reads QTL recapitulation in DRS long-reads dataset m⁶A RNA modifications

We used the 7,658 significant eQTLs already identified using 317 samples from the Illumina RNA-seq data described in Delaneau et al.²³. Only 550 involved genes coding for transcripts affected by RNA modifications tested in the m⁶A RNA modification QTL analysis. To identify the overlap between significant short-read eQTLs and DRS RNA modifications, we retrieved the pvalues associated with the same phenotype-SNP pairs. Subsequently, we computed π_1 using the q-value package in R [35] to estimate the proportion of true discoveries. For false discovery rate (FDR) control, we utilized the qvalue estimation package (v2.18.0) with parameters $\lambda = 0.05$ and FDR = 0.05. An analogous recapitulation analysis was performed for splicing QTLs (sQTLs), yielding 733 genes overlapping between significant short-read sQTLs and transcripts harboring m⁶A modification sites.

Validation of m⁶A modification sites using Yoruba m⁶A-seq data

To validate DRS-detected m⁶A modification sites using an orthogonal approach, we compared predicted modification sites with m⁶A peaks identified in Yoruba LCLs from the 1000 Genomes Project profiled by m⁶A sequencing (m⁶A-seq)³⁸. DRS-detected modification sites mapped to genomic coordinates (see above) were overlapped with Yoruba m⁶A-seq peaks using the *findOverlaps* function from the *GenomicRanges* Bioconductor package (v1.54.0)⁷¹. Overlap was evaluated under two criteria: positional overlap alone, and positional overlap

restricted to modifications and peaks assigned to the same gene. Overlap rates were computed across three modification sets: all DRS-detected modifications (n=17,941), modifications retained after quality filtering and tested for m⁶A-QTL mapping (n=2,761), and significant m⁶A-QTL modifications. For significant m⁶A-QTL hits, replication in the Yoruba m⁶A-QTL dataset was assessed by matching lead SNP-gene pairs between the two datasets and comparing effect directions using the sign of regression beta coefficients.

GWAS overlap and colocalization

To identify genetic variants with known GWAS associations we used the GWAS catalog v1.0.2, accessed March 2026⁴⁴ and we overlapped SNPs with the 87 trQTL and 5 m⁶A-QTL to investigate their possible implication on GWAS-traits. For further colocalization analysis we calculate the probability that a GWAS hit shares the same causal variant as a trQTLs or m⁶A-QTL using bayesian colocalisation analyses as implemented by COLOC (v5.2.3)⁷² and in a subset of GWAS studies. We used GWAS summary statistics from 16 studies listed on **Supplementary Table 11**. SNPs were filtered to keep variants in a 20 kb window around the lead QTL variant. The minor allele frequencies used for the analysis were those from the GWAS summary statistics. We reported the probability that both GWAS and QTLs were shared as $P(H4') = P(H4) / (P(H3) + P(H4))$. Being H3 the probability of both traits to have different causal variants and H4 the probability of both traits sharing the same causal variant.

To evaluate if there was an enrichment in number of overlapping GWAS lead variants from the catalog with trQTLs lead variants (trSNPs), we extracted all SNPs with two properties that matched the original set of trQTL variables, the minor allele frequency had to be within 2% of the original trSNPs, and the distance to the transcription start site of the nearest gene had to be within 500bp. A total of 433 SNPs met these criteria, of those 25 were lead GWAS variants.

Data and code availability

Data was deposited in ENA, under the following accession number PRJEB76585. This includes raw fast5 files. All summary statistics from genetic associations, base-called aligned reads in BAM files and quantifications derived, as well as m⁶A modification information as provided by m⁶Anet were deposited in Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.18763244). Code and further

description of analyses can be found in the first authors github repository:
<https://github.com/aline2593/DRS-LCLs-qtI-analysis>

Authors contribution statement

Conceptualization: AB, ARa, ETD, AV. Methodology: ARe, AB, ARa, AV. Software: ARe, AB, ARa, AV. Validation: ARe, ARa, AV. Formal analysis: ARe, AB, NMRL, ARa, AV. Resources: ARe, GPY, CB. Data curation: ARe, ARa, AV. Writing-original draft: ARe, AB, ARa, AV. Writing- review & editing: ARe, AB, GPY, ARa, AV. Visualization: ARe, ARa, AV. Supervision: AB, JDS, ETD, ARa, AV. Funding acquisition: JDS, ETD, AV.

Competing Interest Statement

None

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